

Figure S1. ¹H 600 MHz metabolomic spectra of adipose tissue extracts from the twelve BN.GK congenic strains and the BN control.

Figure S2. Score plot from O-PLS model of each BN.GK congenic strain against the BN control and corresponding cross-validation with 200 permutations

Fig S2 (cntd)

Correlation coefficient between original and permuted BN and BN.GK-1k

Correlation coefficient between original and permuted BN and BN.GK-1t

Correlation coefficient between original and permuted BN and BN.GK-1d

Correlation coefficient between original and permuted BN and BN.GK-1v

Correlation coefficient between original and permuted BN and BN.GK-1cns

Correlation coefficient between original and permuted BN and BN.GK-1o

Fig. S4. Score plot from O-PLS model of each region of chromosome 1 against other regions and corresponding cross-validation with 200 permutations.

Fig. S4 (Cntd)

